

Analyzing Gandhi's View on Women

Dr. Shibu Paul

Assistant Professor, Department of Political Science
Sripat Singh College, Jiaganj, Murshidabad
West Bengal, India

Abstract

As it is known to all that Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi famous for his tremendous leadership for the freedom movement of India, was a multi-layered personality in the history of modern human civilization. He was not a systemic thinker like Plato or Aristotle but a unique human being with numerous qualities. He was an idealist thinker who had a desire for justice and equality. On the other hand, his rationality was not instrumental or technical rationality, rather, it was much broader in scope, meaning and application. Apart from that, a question may arise, was he also a social reformer and a feminist in true sense or it was the circumstances that made him to become a feminist? This paper is an attempt to explore Gandhiji's contribution for the society and for the emancipation of women in the turbulent period of pre-independence of India.

Key words: idealist, rational, women emancipation, social reformer, feminist.

1. Introduction

Mahatma Gandhi, popularly known as the father of the nation of India, is not considered as a political scientist from traditional point of view. Apart from a successful political leader and freedom fighter, Mahatma Gandhi was a social reformer, a supporter of human rights and a futuristic who believed that women's participation in nation building is the key concept of women empowerment. Because he felt that Swaraj and Freedom would never be possible without the active participation of women who consist half of the total population at that time. He tried to make a space for women in view of the traditional orthodox Indian society in which women were being treated as an inferior sex or subordinate to their male counterpart. He believed that women were superior to men in their moral and spiritual strengths. They had greater powers of self-sacrifice and suffering. They were capable of infinite strength, which they only needed to realize and channelize them. To Gandhi, whom we call 'abala' (weak), when becomes 'Sabala' (empowered), all those powerless become empowered. He also mentioned that 'to call them (women) 'abala' (weak) is to condemn the inherent strength of women; in my view it is an insult to them. Woman is the companion of man, gifted with equal mental capacities. In his own words, 'She has the right to participate in every minute detail in the activities of man and she has equal right of freedom and liberty. By sheer force of vicious customs, even the most ignorant and worthless men have been enjoying a superiority and worthless men have been enjoying a superiority over women which they do not deserve ought not to have.'¹

He suggested that women should not think about their weakness but to think about their inner strength they have. Women must realize themselves as an independent human being and decorate themselves with high qualities as their male companion. He believed that every woman must keep in mind that “Man is born of woman, he is flesh of her and bone of her bone. Come to your own and deliver your message again.”ⁱⁱ

Gandhi's belief on Women

The word ‘women empowerment’ nowadays has become a fashionable and buzz word. Basically, women empowerment means, authorization of women or participation of women with confidence in all spheres of life, a way of independence, capability to resist discrimination obligatory to the male dominated society. It does not mean to dominate over men but to understand the rights and dignity she deserves. It was very hard to think about women emancipation during that period but the Mahatma did it. He firmly opined that ‘India’s salvation depends on the sacrifice and enlightenment of her women’.ⁱⁱⁱ

The basic reason of his curiosity regarding the emancipation of women at that time was to engage maximum number of females into the freedom movement. He believed that the rest of the total population that consist of women might change the future of India under the British rule. He has immense faith in their determination, spirit of service and sacrifice. He firmly declared that women must have votes and an equal legal status. And it would definitely affect the political deliberations of the nation. He was inspired by the tremendous success obtained by women politicians’ of ex-colonial countries like South Africa. In his own words, “My contribution to the great problem (of women’s role in society) lies in my presenting for acceptance of truth and ahimsa in every walk of life, whether for individuals or nations. I have hugged the hope that in this, woman will be unquestioned leader and having thus found her place in human evolution, will shed her inferiority complex Women’s entry into national politics through non-violent methods bought miraculous results.”^{iv} He realized that it was not an easy but very challenging task. He understood that the root of the cause of women’s subordination lied in various kind of societal customs and traditional rituals that prevented the way of development for women. So, he attacked on the root cause of subordination of women in India.

Gandhi On Rigid Customs

According the Gandhiji, “the ideal that marriage aims at, the spiritual union through the physical. The human love that it incarnates in intended to serve as a stepping stone to divine or universal love.”^v It is clear, to Gandhi, marriage is a sacred institution connected with the spirit of two individuals. The true purpose of marriage should be and in intimate friendship and companionship between man and woman. But he was very disappointed with child marriage system at that time. Because, in traditional Indian society, girls were supposed to be treated as a burden of the family. Child marriages were being conducted to get rid of this burden. Gandhiji was totally against of it and said, “it is wholly wrong of parents to force marriage on their daughters.”^{vi} He questioned the custom of ‘Kanyadan’ in the case of child marriage. According to him, a father is the protector of his child not the owner.^{vii} Child marriage not only destroys the childhood but also it affects the mental health as well as physical growth of the children. He supported legislation which prohibited child marriage like the Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1929.

At the same time, he protested against another social evil of dowry. To him, it was better to remain unmarried rather giving dowry. He called this custom as pernicious as it lowered the status of women, destroyed their sense of equality with men and defiled the institution of marriage.^{viii}

He also believed that 'Purdah' (veil) system in Indian society is an inhuman and immoral. It weakened instead of strengthening morality for it did not in preserving chastity as chastity is not a hot house growth and cannot be superimposed.^{ix} He believed that the veil generates the feeling of insecurity in women and results in deterioration of their health. He appealed in public to abolish the system of 'Purdah' and let the women to come out of their house and become an active participant in the struggle for freedom of the country.^x

He was very much concern about the condition of child widows who were not allowed to re-marry. They were treated badly socially. The presence of a widow in a celebration seemed to be an omen. He considered it to be his good fortune to see a widow in the early hour of the day. He regarded her blessing to be a great boon.^{xi} He advised every family to treat widow with utmost respect and to give her facilities to expand her knowledge.^{xii}

Gandhiji was very much aware of the inhuman 'Sati' in that time. It was a brutal custom created based on the misinterpretation of Sastras and Puranas by a section of orthodox people. He argued that if wife must prove her loyalty and undivided devotion to her husband, then the husband must also prove his allegiance and devotion to his wife.^{xiii}

In the structure of traditional patriarchal Indian society, married women were treated as husband's bondslaves. It creates superior- subordinate relationship, an artificial relation in which two individuals are inter-connected physically but not spiritually. To him, child marriage is a heinous sin and inhuman act. He opines, "the custom of child marriage is both a moral as well as a physical evil. For it undermines of our morals and induces physical degeneration." He believed that customs and rituals are very much necessary in people's lives but these should not be overruled on morality and humanity. In his own words, "It is good to swim in the water of tradition, but to sink in them is suicide."^{xiv} By countenancing such customs, we recede from God, as well as Swaraj.^{xv} His own experience of early marriage at a tender age and the resultant difficulties made him discourage this practice vehemently.

In traditional patriarchal societies, it is believed that women should confined to their families and under legal and customary subjection of their male family members. In 'Manu Samhita', women were regarded as the root cause of all evil and responsible for downfall of men. But Gandhiji rejected these ideas which were injurious to women and girls even if such practices had sanctioned in Dharma Shastra, law and tradition. He believed that customs and practices like female infanticide, female illiteracy, dowry, polygamy, sati, repeated pregnancies, permanent and pathetic widowhood, wife beating and verbal abuse made life of common women very hard. These kinds of injustice are remained just because that women are not given space to uplift themselves.

Gandhi on Division of Labour

According to Gandhi, equality of sexes did not mean equality of occupations and nor did it mean equality in the realm of work and power. He was in favour of maintaining a harmonious division of labours between men and women which had been operative since the time of Adam that persists to the present day. 'Adam wove and Eve span.'^{xvi} He did not believe in women working for wages or engagement in a commercial enterprise. He believed that fundamentally men and women are one, but some point there was a vital difference between them. Hence, the occupations of the two must also be different. He was of opinion that in rural India, women play a vital role as agricultural labourer. Thus, this was the most natural division of sphere of work. The duty of motherhood needs special qualities which men need not to possess. She is the essentially mistress of the house. He is the bread winner; she is the keeper and distributor of the bread.^{xvii} But he challenged the idea of rigid division of labour between men and women. Actually, he did not want to hit the basic so called traditional relationship of men and women at that turbulent period.

Gandhi's Voice for Common Women

It is only Gandhi as a political leader felt that women's participation in independence movement would have changed the scenario. He was aware of the fact that women are powerful force in society but they were overlooked and suppressed. He believed that the image of new woman would have changed for the sake of India's freedom. But in the name of cultural and emotional tradition, the potentiality of women power would have never been discovered. To him, "It is good to swim in the waters of tradition, but to sink in them is suicide."^{xviii} A new type of relationship between man and woman would play an important role in future. Gandhi's words reflected his entire social, political philosophy and techniques of mass action. He gave the example of Sita, Draupadi and Damyanti who were the ideals of Indian womanhood. But the Sita and Draupadi of Gandhi was not the commonly accepted lifeless stereotype of subservience. Gandhi's Sita was used as a symbol of Swadeshi, to convey an anti-imperialist message. Sita who used to wear 'cloth made in India' or homespun and thus kept her heart and body pure.^{xix} Furthermore, 'Sita was no slave of Rama'.^{xx} To him, Sita was not a helpless creature. He portrayed Sita as a confident woman with a moral courage. He advised all Indian women not to consider themselves 'abalas' but rather to be like Draupadi who was a symbol of 'robust independence'.^{xxi} He further thought that power and courage were not the monopoly of men. To him, physically strong, psychologically and morally confident women could change the scenario of India under the British Rule. And the first and foremost thing is to educate our wives, mothers and sisters. Thus, liberation of women from every kind of social barriers. In his own words, "If they believe that freedom is the birthright of every nation and individual' and if they were determined to achieve it, then they should first liberate their women from evils customs and conventions that restrict their all-round healthy growth'.^{xxii} He believed that Swaraj is not possible without social reform.

Conclusion

There is no doubt that Mahatma Gandhi was neither feminist nor anti-feminist, rather he was a great human soul. He just wanted to uplift the women who were in deplorable condition, and out of reach of social, economic and political rights. And he was very much aware of the fact that India under British Rule need a mass action with full force. It was true that it was not possible without active participation of women who were the half of the population of that time. His prime objective was to involve maximum number of women in the freedom struggle for India's independence. He advised all the women to be strong morally and psychologically. But at the same time, he sought to change not so much the material condition of women. He did not realize to put an economic content into his concept of women emancipation. He tried to change women's position without transforming their outer world of production or the inner world of the family, sexuality and reproduction. He did not want to make fundamental change in the traditional relationship between men and women. Because he knew very well that it might be boomerang if he would try to change the primary relationship of men and women of traditional Indian society at that time.

References

- ⁱ Gandhi on Women: Collection of Mahatma Gandhi's Writings and Speeches on Women, Source: <https://www.azquotes.com/quote/602685>, p.425
- ⁱⁱ The Mind of Mahatma Gandhi; Women's Status and Role in Society, Source: <https://www.mkgandhi.org/momgandhi/c/hap60.htm>.
- ⁱⁱⁱ Ibid.p.425
- ^{iv} R. P. Mishra: Rediscovering Gandhi; Volume I: Hind Swaraj-Gandhi's Challenges to modern Civilization; Concept Publishing Company, New Delhi
- ^v Young India, 21-5-1931, p. 115.
- ^{vi} Harijan, 15-9-1946, p.311
- ^{vii} Young India, 3-1-1929
- ^{viii} Bakshi, S.R, Gandhi and His Social Thought, Criterion Publications, New Delhi, 1986, p. 175.
- ^{ix} Gandhi, M.K, Women, Navjivan Publishing House, Ahmedabad, 1958, p. 22.
- ^x Gandhi, M.K, Women and Social Injustice, Navjivan Publishing House, Ahmedabad, 1942, p. 96.
- ^{xi} Child marriage not only destroys the childhood but also it affects the mental health as well as physical growth of the children. He supported legislation which prohibited child marriage like the Child Marriage Restraint Act of 1929.
- ^{xii} Jain, Simmi, Encyclopedia of Women Through the Ages, p. 130.
- ^{xiii} Gandhi, M. K, Social Service, Work and Reform, Vol. 2, p. 153.
- ^{xiv} Kishwar, Madhu. Traditions Are Not Bad but They Need to Evolve Constantly. The Economic times. New Delhi. January 29 2017.
- ^{xv} Harijan, 01-06-1928.
- ^{xvi} CW, Vol. LXX, p. 381, Harijan, (2 December, 1939)
- ^{xvii} Harijan (24 Feb, 1940. CW, Vol. LXXI, p. 207-8.
- ^{xviii} Navajivan (28 June, 1925) CW, Vol. XXVII, p.308
- ^{xix} CW, Vol. XXVII, p.126. Speech at women's meeting, Mymensingh, 19 May, 1925
- ^{xx} Young India (21 October, 1925, CW, Vol. XXXI, p.511.
- ^{xxi} Young India (24 March, 1927), cited in A. Hingorani (ed.)' To the Women', Gandhi Series, Vol. II, (Karachi, 2nd ed, 1943), p, 24.
- ^{xxii} CW, Vol. XL, pp.416-17, 23 May, 1929.